

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF ADDUCTS OF COPPER(II) BENZOATE

Sr.No.	Compound	Colour	%Cu		%N	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (α -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N)	Green	16.14	15.94	3.55	3.51
2.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (β -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N)	Green	15.80	15.94	3.57	3.51
3.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (γ -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N)	Green	16.07	15.94	3.57	3.51
4.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (Iso-C ₅ H ₇ N)	Green	14.45	14.62	3.48	3.22
5.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (β -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂	Blue	12.64	12.93	6.04	5.70
6.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (γ -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂	Blue	12.99	12.93	6.04	5.70
7.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (Iso-C ₅ H ₇ N) ₂	Blue	11.35	11.28	5.13	4.97

An attempt to convert 1 : 1 adduct of isoquinoline into 1 : 2 adduct however has failed.

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Coordination Complexes of Cobalt Chloride with Cinchonine and Quinine

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SINCE after the discovery of vitamin B-12, cobalt chloride is being used in various antianaemic formulations. Malaria is generally followed by anaemia and quinine is an established antimalarial drug. It was therefore, desired to study complexes of cobalt chloride with cinchonine and quinine.

In the literature Vascautanu and Jurca¹ seem to have prepared complexes of cobalt chloride with cinchonine and quinine of the compositions cinchonine₂-(CoCl₂)₃ and quinine-(CoCl₂)₂ and quinine-(CoCl₂)₃.H₂O. These proportions however, do not appear to be convincing. These authors do not seem to have studied the nature of the complexes. Herein we describe the conductometric, spectrophotometric and analytical studies of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Composition and Stability of the complexes :

Cinchonine and quinine were of extra pure grade; cobalt chloride and other materials were of Analar quality.

Preliminary conductometric titrations at 30° ± 0.5° of ligands against cobalt chloride and absorbance studies on 'spekol' of their equimolar solutions using Vosdburgh and Cooper² method indicated 1:1 complexation, λ_{max} for cinchoninecobalt chloride and quinine-cobalt chloride being 345 and 350 nm.

Formation of 1 : 1 complex was further confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation³, mole ratio⁴ and slope ratio⁵ methods using absorbance as the index property.

The stability constants have been evaluated from Job's curves^{6,7} and Yoe Jones curves⁸ for cinchonine and quinine cobalt chloride complexes. The results are given in Table 1.

Ethanollic solutions of cobalt chloride and ligand were mixed and refluxed on water bath for about 4 hrs when a blue coloured complex was obtained which was cooled, filtered and washed with alcohol and ether.

Cobalt was estimated as tetrapyridine cobalt dithiocyanate⁹ after removing the base, nitrogen by modified Kjeldahl's method, chloride as silver chloride and water by heating to 110° till constant weight. The results are given in Table 2.

All these results point to analogous compositions for cobalt chloride complexes of cinchonine and quinine. Considering the fact that each of the two nitrogen and the oxygen of the secondary alcoholic group in the molecules of cinchonine and quinine

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TABLE 1

Complex CoCl ₂ with :	log K			Corresponding ΔF KCal/mole		
	Job's Curve	Yoe Jones's curve				
Cinchonine	7.67	8.36	8.65	-10.58	-11.61	-12.00
Quinine	8.47	8.03	8.38	-11.71	-11.14	-11.63

TABLE 2

Molecular formula	Percentage	Co	Cl	N	H ₂ O
C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ON ₂ .CoCl ₂ .H ₂ O (Cinchonine)	Found	12.60	16.12	5.82	3.23
	Required	13.35	16.04	6.34	4.07
C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .CoCl ₂ .H ₂ O (Quinine)	Found	11.91	15.09	5.08	4.23
	Required	12.49	15.03	5.93	3.81

are capable of donation, the structure (I) may be assigned to cobalt chloride-cinchonine (R = H) and cobalt chloride-quinine (R = OCH₃) complexes. The structure (I) involves 7 and 8 membered rings which are not unlikely¹⁰ in coordination chemistry.

Structure (I) gets support from the fact that in the I.R. spectra of these complexes, metal-nitrogen absorption band is observed at 645 cm⁻¹ in cobalt chloride-quinine complex and metal-oxygen absorption bands are observed at 680 cm⁻¹ in both the complexes similar to Co-acetyl acetate. Further, absorption bands at 820, 3100 and 3500 cm⁻¹ in these complexes indicate co-ordinated water molecule.

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Manganese(III) Complexes with Aryl Schiff Bases

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RECENTLY Schiff bases with more than one coordinating centres have been used to stabilise manganese(III) ion¹⁻⁹. In continuation of our work on manganese(III) complexes¹⁰, we report now the

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